

Understanding the effect of biofilm development on drug resistance in clinical isolates of Hypervirulent *Klebsiella pneumoniae*

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Keywords

Hypervirulent *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, Classical *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, biofilm, Antibiotic resistant pattern

Abstract

The ability of hypervirulent *Klebsiella pneumoniae*'s (hvKp's) biofilm production dispersion remains unclear. The present study aimed to correlate the hvKp biofilm formation and its impact on resistance with its drug resistant pattern. A total of 100 clinical isolates were taken for the study. Out of these, 22 isolates hypervirulence gene (rmpA gene). Among these 22 isolates 17 isolates (77%) showed biofilm production. Further, hvKp strains with the ability to produce biofilm showed higher resistant to antibiotic than the classical *Klebsiella pneumoniae*'s (cKp's) tested antibiotics include ceftriaxone/cefotaxime 17(100%), ciprofloxacin/ Norfloxacin 14 (82.4%), Gentamicin 14 (82.4%) Amikacin 8 (47.1%), Imipenem 10 (58.8%), Meropenem 10 (58.8%), Piperacillin+tazobactam 5(29.4%), Fosfomycin 3 (17.6%). Thus, the results indicate that the presence of hvKp strains with their heightened propensity for the production biofilms poses significant clinical risk that must be addressed for effective management.

1 Introduction

Klebsiella pneumoniae (*K. pneumoniae*) is an opportunistic pathogen causing a wide range of infections. *K. pneumoniae* commonly causes nosocomial infections, particularly in intensive care units, such as urinary tract and bloodstream infections [3&4]. The presence of virulence components, such as capsular antigens, lipopolysaccharide, adhesions, and siderophores, which are necessary for survival, adaptation, and immune evasion during infection, has been connected to the pathogenicity of this organism. Traditionally, *K. pneumoniae* infection were found more often in immunocompromised individuals. *K. pneumoniae*, is one of the few gram-negative rods that can cause primary pneumonia [1], a major causative agent of nosocomial pneumonia [2]. Concerningly, hypervirulent strains *K. pneumoniae* (hvKp) can infect healthy people with potentially fatal illnesses. Further, it is also noted that these hypervirulent strains of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* is more resistant against the antibiotics than the classical *K. pneumoniae* [5]. Even though hvKp strains is known well for their antibiotic resistance, the mechanism behind this heightened resistance is not known yet. Therefore, determining the factors contributing to hypervirulence *K.*

pneumoniae is crucial. The inherited causes of large virulence plasmids and chromosomal mobile genetic elements are frequently reported to exhibit hypervirulence, and these traits can be utilized as biomarkers to differentiate clinical isolates of hvKp from cKp. The emergence of hypervirulent strains that are alarmingly resistant to drugs has presented a new difficulty in the fight against an already deadly infection.

Among several factors contributing to the pathogenicity, it is thought that one of the most crucial colonization strategies used by pathogenic *K. pneumoniae* strains is the capacity to build a biofilm. Biofilms have been linked to increased resistance to antimicrobial drugs, which in turn promotes treatment failure and microbial infection persistence [6]. Thus, in the present study the ability of the hypervirulent strains of *K. pneumoniae* is tested for biofilm production and correlated it with antibiotic resistance. The development of biofilms increases resistance to antimicrobial agents and external stresses. The development of microcolonies, biofilm maturation, additional organization, and at the end, the detachment of planktonic cells that can proliferate and colonize or infect sites nearby or at distant sites are all carefully orchestrated processes that occur during the formation of biofilms.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Study design, and sample size

In all, 100 unique isolates of *K. pneumoniae* from MGMCRI, which were obtained from both inpatients and outpatients between August 2021 and April 2022, were recovered from a various clinical specimen, including urine, sputum, us, blood, and other miscellaneous specimens.

According to 2020 Clinical & Laboratory Standards Institute: CLSI Guidelines the disk diffusion test was used to determine the antibiotic susceptibility of cultured *K. pneumoniae* [7]. After plating the grown cells uniformly on Mueller Hinton agar, they were given a five-minute drying period. Antibiotic disks (HiMedia Laboratories), including cotrimoxazole (10mcg), ceftriaxone /cefotaxime (10/30 mcg), Ciprofloxacin/Norfloxacin (5/10 mcg), Gentamicin (10 mcg), Amikacin (30 mcg), Imipenem (10 mcg), Meropenem (10 mcg), Piperacillin+Tazobactam (100/10 mcg), Cefperazone+Sulbactam (100/10 mcg), Fosfomycin (200 mcg) were placed on the surface of the agar using sterilized forceps. Using a metric ruler, the diameters of the inhibition zones were measured following a 24-hour incubation period at 37 degrees Celsius. The hypervirulence genes (*rmpA* and *magA*) were detected by using conventional PCR. Biofilm production detected by using microtiter plate method. The statistical analysis had been performed by using SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) statistics software for Windows, version 15 (which is available from SPSS Inc., Chicago, USA). The P- value < 0.05 had been taken as a statistically significant.

2.2 Biofilm Formation Assay

The quantitative adhesion assay was used to perform the biofilm production. Briefly, the overnight culture of individual isolate maintained at 37 °C in trypticase soy broth was taken. 198 µl of Tryptic Soy Broth (TSB) was enclosed in 96 well sterile flat bottom plates and inoculated with 2 µl of cell suspension. 200 µl of uninoculated TSB were also included in each test as negative control wells. The incubation temperature was kept at 37 °C for 24 hours. After incubation three gentle washes with phosphate buffered saline were performed and air dried. 50 µl of 0.1% safranin was added to stained the biofilm for 15 minutes. After utilizing 200 µl of distilled water to gently clean the wells three times, they were dried upside down. In the end, 200 µl of 5% isopropanol were used to dissolve the wells and solubilize the pigmented biofilm mass. Using a microplate reader, an optical density (OD) measurement was made at 570 nm. The mean OD was determined by looking at each isolate

or negative control for eight to twelve wells. Optical Density Cut-off (ODC) was assigned as an average OD of negative controls + (3* Standard Deviation (SD) of negative controls). Isolate with $OD \leq ODC$ categorized as non-Biofilm producer. Meanwhile, the isolate was categorized as biofilm producer consisting of weak biofilm producer if $2*ODC < OD \leq 4*ODC$; moderate $2*ODC < OD \leq 4*ODC$; and strong biofilm producer if $OD > 4* ODC$ [8].

2.3 Polymerase Chain Reaction

Using a commercially available DNA extraction kit (HiMedia, India), the preserved samples DNA was extracted, and the target gene (*rmpA*) was amplified in a thermal cycler (CFX 96, Bio-Rad, California, USA) with the proper primers (Sigma-Aldrich) and master mix (Amplicon).

The primer for

rmpA-	-F-5'ACTGGGCTACCTCTGCTTCA-3', R5'CTTGCATGAGCCATCTTTCA-3' [9]
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were used respectively. The polymerase chain reaction (PCR) cycle involving denaturation, primer annealing, extension and terminal extension was set at 95 degrees Celsius for 30s, 60 degrees Celsius for 90s, 72 degrees Celsius for 60s and 72 degrees Celsius for 10 minutes respectively. The amplicons were visualized using ethidium bromide staining in 2% agarose gel electrophoresis.

The amplicon size of *rmpA* gene were 516 base pair respectively.

3 Results

A total of 100 isolates were studied. Out of hundred isolates, twenty-two isolates expressed hypervirulence gene. Among the 22 isolates, seventeen isolates (77%) showed biofilm production the *hypervirulent Klebsiella pneumoniae* showed more resistant than classical *Klebsiella pneumoniae* towards some classes of antibiotics in biofilm production. They are ceftriaxone/cefotaxime 17(100%), ciprofloxacin/ Norfloxacin 14 (82.4%), Gentamicin 14 (82.4%) Amikacin 8 (47.1%), Imipenem 10 (58.8%), Meropenem 10 (58.8%), Piperacillin+ tazobactam 5(29.4%), Fosfomycin 3 (17.6%).

Table – 1: Association of drug resistance with biofilm cKp and hvKp

Antibiotics	Biofilm Ckp N=89	Biofilm Hvkp N=22	P-value
Cotrimoxazole	11(22.9%)	14(82.4%)	0
Ceftriaxone/ cefotaxime	36(75.0%)	17 (100.0%)	0.027##
Ciprofloxacin/ Norfloxacin	19(39.6%)	14(82.4%)	0.002#
Gentamicin	13(27.1%)	14(82.4%)	0
Amikacin	9(18.8%)	8(47.1%)	0.049##
Imipenem	9(18.8%)	10(58.8%)	0.004##
Meropenem	10(20.8%)	10(58.8%)	0.004##
Piperacillin+Tazobactam	2(4.2%)	5(29.4%)	0.011#
Cefoperazone+ sulbactam	8(16.7%)	6(35.3%)	0.167
Fosfomycin	1(2.1%)	3(17.6%)	0.052#

#,##- statistically significant (chi-square test-#& Fischer exact test-## applied).

Figure-1: Biofilm production in Microtitre plate Method

4 Discussion

K. pneumoniae has become a significant pathogen that accounts for 20% of infections in hospitals across the globe [10]. The ability to produce biofilm is one of the many characteristics that made *K. pneumoniae* more virulent. Most of the isolates used in this investigation exhibit their ability to produce biofilms. The ability of *K. pneumoniae* to produce biofilm increases the persistence of the *K. pneumoniae* species and shields it from antibiotic action and host immunological responses [11]. *K. pneumoniae* is capable of producing biofilms, which are groups of cells submerged in an extracellular polymeric substance consisting of proteins, DNA, exopolysaccharides, and lipopeptides. These cells can stick to surfaces or to each other. Antibiotic effects and immune defenses mechanisms can be neutralized by biofilm, shielding the bacterium. *K. pneumoniae* has the ability to produce a thick layer of extracellular biofilm, which diminishes the effects of antibiotics and helps microbes adhere to both living and non-living surfaces [12]. In our study, we detected 17(77%) isolates produce biofilm production in hypervirulent *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. It's probable that the biofilm made by hvkp strains makes the infection more invasive since it allows the organisms to colonize in the gastrointestinal, respiratory, and urinary tracts. It is well recognized that biofilm helps shield against medicines and immune defense mechanisms, which stimulates hvkp resistance to antimicrobial medications [13 & 14]. Antibiotics utilized in this investigation had no impact on the almost all of our isolates, including the hvkp isolates. Hvkp was demonstrated to be the most antibiotic sensitive, but more recently, evidence of the emergence of antimicrobial resistance has been reported [15]. When compared to isolates that are not tissue invasive, it was demonstrated that hvKp is a vigorous biofilm producer in the laboratory [16].

5 Conclusions

The recent investigation demonstrated that hvkp strains exist and their propensity to produce biofilms is increasing, posing a significant clinical risk that requires attention to stop its spread. Compared to classical *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (ckp), hypervirulent *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (hvKp) has a tendency to acquire antibiotic resistance and biofilm production in clinical isolates. Numerous virulence factors help bacterial competitors produce biofilms in their colonizing habitat. Many of these substances have been studied as possible targets for new antibacterial medications or as possibilities for vaccinations. The evaluation of this virulent should be the main objective of systemic surveillance. Clones that are resistant to drugs and that produce biofilms could be advantageous in the face of this global public health problem and other challenges in the future.

Competing of Interest: The author declares no competing of interest.

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